

THE IMPACT OF THE COVID 19 ON SOCIAL ECONOMY ENTERPRISES IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

Purpose – The objective of this study is to show how a social enterprise communicates social activities online according to its statutory mission, as well as their reporting against COVID-19.

Methodology - This study is exploratory and descriptive, it includes 67 social enterprises with web pages, out of a total of 2649 social enterprises registered in the Single Registry of Social Enterprises in Romania.

Findings – Most of the Social enterprises that have a website are small enterprises that have understood the importance of communicating social activities but also the impact of disseminating them to the all stakeholders.

Originality/value – This article contributes to the literature by evaluating the way in which social enterprise in Romania communicates social economy actions online, being the first representative study of this kind in Romania.

Key words: social economy; communication; website; COVID-19.

Introduction

The social economy environment has started to develop considerably in recent years in Romania, as well as in the European Union (EU), with over 2 million social economy enterprises in Europe at the moment, representing 10% of all enterprises in the EU. More than 11 million people – around 6% of EU employees – work for social economy enterprises (EU, 2021).

Thus, social economy enterprises contribute to EU policies on employment, social cohesion, regional and rural development, environmental protection, consumer protection, agriculture, third country development and social security.

Starting from the previously presented, we conduct the study on the social economy sector, the database obtained from the unique record register of social enterprises in Romania, of the National Employment Agency (AJOFM), in June 2022, there were 2649 social enterprises (figure 1), of which most were established in Alba county (AJOFM, 2022).

In Romania, the emphasis is on the social economy as a tool for social inclusion and combating poverty, and activities that do not fulfill this role, but are recognized at European level, can be carried out according to the principle "what is not prohibited is permitted" as they are neither limited nor prohibited by the respective provisions (Haarich, et al, 2020). These activities will be carried out in compliance with other existing legal provisions, but they do not benefit from promotion and support through the support mechanisms of the Social Economy during the COVID-19 pandemic they were quite affected (OECD, 2020; Cioca & Bratu, 2021). In this way, the need to complete the existing legal provisions with an extended definition of the Social Economy, including other forms than those that directly contribute to social inclusion (Lakatos et. all, 2020) is found.

Figure 1. The evolution of the number of new certified social enterprises in Romania

This study, due to the importance of the development of the social economy sector in Romania, due to structural funds, as well as the technological impact, in order to investigate online communication, within social enterprises, in terms of the statutory mission, as well as the effect of the COVID-19 in their way of communication. Starting from the purpose and characteristics of our study, the data regarding the communication of social enterprises in Romania are collected from their websites.

Methodology

In order to carry out the current analysis regarding the online situation related to the reporting mode of the social economy of social enterprises, we selected the database provided by the National Agency for Employment, from the single record register of social enterprises. The database contains over 2649 social enterprises, which form the basis for opportunities related to the development of social business as well as commercial relations. The AJOFM database provides information on the social enterprise sector in Romania, such as the field of activity, certification as a social enterprise, social brand, social enterprise technical and financial data, but also contact information, but, unfortunately, only 67 social enterprises had a website dedicate to this social business. We set out to use the entire sample of 67 social enterprises in our study to analyze their websites to investigate how they communicate social economy activities, presentation style and their reporting on COVID-19. In the same way, we checked if the website of the social enterprises from the selected sample is functional, as well as the balance sheet in order to be able to grant the necessary resources for social development and statutory activity.

According to the Permanent European Conference of Cooperatives, Mutual Societies, Associations and Foundations (CEP-CMAF) (Lakatos, et. all, 2020), the broad prerogative of the social economy concept includes many types of activities and projects that are a catalyst for sustainable development of society through Social economy enterprises are economic and social actors with ramifications in all sectors, characterized primarily by their social mission and specific entrepreneurial objectives. "The social economy includes organizations such as cooperatives, mutual societies, associations and foundations. These enterprises are particularly active in certain areas such as: social protection, social services, health, banks, insurance, agricultural production, proximity services, education and training, culture, sports and recreational activities..." etc. To carry out the study we analyzed on the websites of social enterprises information on projects that can contribute to the social mission towards consumers, employees, as well as other interested parties. At the same time, we searched for information related to the activities carried out according to the social mission, in the communities where they come from, as well as in general (Aikat, 2000; Lakatos, et al. 2012).

In the current study, we will analyze the role that the Internet has in online communication of Romanian social enterprises. We chose social websites from Romania as a research topic, because they have taken a considerable lead in terms of development and how to adapt to new technologies. This study

shows how the accessibility of internet interacts and also analyzes how they relate to the social economy.

At the same time, we will analyze the importance and characteristics of online communications, taking into account the style and content of websites. Social enterprises invest more and more resources in different social economy activities, which indicates that social enterprises are aware of their social role and express their voluntary desire to publicly communicate their results, to impact stakeholders, as well as to obtain on the one hand added value and potential benefits for the social business.

The growing interest in the communication of social activities as well as social missions indicates that it becomes a need for social enterprises to communicate as actively as possible in the field of the social economy in order to be more competitive. Therefore, the fact that the Internet is more accessible in today's world and an indispensable way to communicate, will make our study more interesting for social enterprises, which have now either decided not to use this tool at the beginning of the journey, or consider it unimportant. Our study would also be useful in the evaluation/classification of social enterprises and as an example for the importance of using the Internet in their current activities. Social economy activities according to statutory missions, develop with small steps, but sustainable, and with the will to communicate and implement the social way, even starting from the side of social enterprises, especially with the help of a tool like the Internet. Therefore, in this study we analyzed the availability of the websites of these social enterprises, as well as the communication of their social economy activities on their one websites, in order to have the clearest and most complete communication situation of social enterprises from Romania. The study will provide a clearer situation for managers regarding how to improve the quality of social enterprise communication and the sites in terms of style and to convey a good image of social enterprise.

In this study, we will also expand the existing knowledge area in the specialized literature regarding the use of the Internet by social enterprises and the reporting of social economy activities. Communication regarding social economy activities is a little analyzed area (Chui et al., 2012) and online communication strategies are very little analyzed (Dachs, 2018), therefore this study adds to the existing specialized literature, analyzing how online communication is done in social economy activities of social enterprises in Romania.

In order to investigate how social enterprises in Romania communicate their social activities according to statutory missions on their websites, the study proposes the following questions in order to define the research methodology:

1. How obvious is the communication of social mission according to statutory missions on the websites of social enterprises?
2. Do social enterprises in Romania communicate their commitment?
3. How is social activity communication presented on websites?
4. How do social enterprises communicate the aspects related to COVID-19?

In carrying out the study, a coding system was developed. Thus, the analysis of the sites in the sample was carried out between June and July 2022. This analysis was carried out using the Internet through the Google Chrome search engine and a form filled in accordance with the information provided on the websites. This grid was developed according to the works analyzing web content (Pollach, 2003). The social enterprises were chosen randomly from a database provided by the National Agency for Employment, from the single register of records of social enterprises. The websites samples were examined in order to analyze the information about the activities of the social economy, in terms of presentation and their relevance to COVID-19.

The study includes 67 social enterprises with web pages, out of a total of 2,649 social enterprises registered in the Single Registry of Social Enterprises in Romania and is descriptive and exploratory. We should also highlighted that the analysis regarding the reporting of social activity according to statutory missions based on web analysis carried out on social enterprises in Romania is limited.

Results

From 67 social enterprises used in our analysis, 31.34% had a section dedicated to social activities. Before excluding the other social enterprises from our analysis, we used key words filtered such as social, social economy social entrepreneurship, social engagement, social development community and

philanthropy. The social enterprises in the final sample of 47 operated in several social activities according to the statutory mission.

In our analysis, we searched websites for links dedicated to aspects related to the social economy in accordance with the statutory mission. Out of the 47 sites, more than 46.27% social enterprises had a link on their page or had it mentioned in a subsection like "about us" / "home". At the same time the websites should have a separate section for information on social activities carried out according to the statutory mission their consumers can reach without significant effort. We see that these 25.37% social enterprises understand the necessity and importance of presenting their social engagement in a visible way, on their one website. More than a quarter of the social enterprises in the sample (37.31% social enterprises) present their work results in more than two pages and most of them adding some images. A total of 32.84% social enterprises had only one page with information. Regarding the number of pages dedicated to the social cause, it is a very simple and useful measure, but it is a measure open to criticism, so I used this method proposed by Aikat (2000).

To examine the communication content of online social economy activities, we also analyzed websites for additional social information such as press clippings, annual reports and awards. We can say that most projects can be considered charity events or philanthropic projects, we noticed that about a quarter of social enterprises (23.88%) declared their one projects and the greeting message or a visit from a personality on their website.

We can see that only 13.43% of social enterprises have a page dedicated to communication with COVID-19 prevention and the necessary actions. Other social enterprises have references to sources from newspapers or reports added to the social section that show the results of their activity (41.79%%). The findings of our analysis are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The results of the research regarding the communication of social enterprises in Romania

Indicators analyzed	No of social enterprises	%
Size of the investigated sample	67	2.53%
The website functionality	47	70.15%
Facebook pages	37	55.22%
<i>Features regarding the social economy and the impact of COVID-19</i>		
Websites with a social economy section	21	31.34%
Websites with a section on COVID-19	9	13.43%
<i>Characteristics of communication in the social section</i>		
In the main page	31	46.27%
In other pages	15	22.39%
<i>The degree of coverage with social information</i>		
1 page	22	32.84%
2-3 pages	25	37.31%
More than 3 pages	17	25.37%
<i>Social content related daily activity</i>		
Projects for the social economy	16	23.88%
Social mission communication activities	30	44.78%
Detailed report	12	17.91%
<i>The way of presenting social activities</i>		
Only text	14	20.90%
Text with visual effects	28	41.79%
Multimedia	11	16.42%
Feedback section	29	43.28%

Regarding the importance of the Internet, we can say that it is the environment with the most dynamic growth in all of history and continues to dominate the marketing budgets of social enterprises thanks to consumers who turn to it more and more. Thus, the design of content and websites, as well as advertisements, becomes imperative (Geissler, 2001; Arora et.all, 2020). Consequently, we studied the format and presentation style of documents regarding social economy activities according to the statutory mission.

To classify the presentation of social economy activities, we had three options: text, images, text accompanied by visual effects and multimedia. Related to the interactive features of the multimedia section, only 16.42% social enterprises used multimedia in their social activities section, in the form of video streaming. Regarding interactivity or features that facilitate two-way communication, only 43.28% of social enterprises had a feedback section, but most social enterprises in the sample had contact information where questions could be asked via e-mail related to general information and social economy activities according to the statutory mission.

More than 41.79% of the social enterprises used text accompanied by visual effects in the presentation of information related to the social activity according to the statutory mission.

Conclusions

The conclusions showed that the number of social enterprises with information about social activities according to the statutory mission on their sites being limited. Social enterprises do not maximize the potential of sites to their benefit in terms of style and quantity. However, the study provides an overview of the various social economy activities in Romania.

The research used the sample from the database of the single record register of social enterprises in Romania, of the National Employment Agency in Romania, so the results are representative, and they are consistent with the results of similar studies.

The study enriches the existing specialized literature and offers future research perspectives, as well as a good knowledge of the basic principles for a better use of web resources by managers. Also addressed, online social economy activities according to the statutory mission that could be interesting for organizations and tips in order to empower their websites for a better style and image of good governance received from feedback.

The study analyzes the current situation of online communication of social economy activities according to the statutory mission and shows that even social enterprises are much more concerned with the social and responsible communication of their activities with the various interested parties, through the Internet. Although the vast majority of social enterprises are small enterprises, the communication regarding COVID-19 was quite limited, an aspect that denotes either the limited degree of impact of this pandemic on daily activity, as well as an adjacent field that does not involve this aspect in daily activity of enterprises.

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